

DIAMAS

Developing Institutional Open Access
Publishing Models to Advance
Scholarly Communication

Funded by
the European Union

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Diamond Open Access Standard (DOAS)

DOAS sets out standards for Diamond Open Access publishing that help scholarly publishers ensure quality and transparency in journal publishing processes. It addresses the seven core components of scholarly publishing:

1. Funding
2. Legal ownership, mission and governance
3. Open Science
4. Editorial management, editorial quality and research integrity
5. Technical service efficiency
6. Visibility, communication, marketing, and impact
7. Equity, Diversity, Inclusion and Belonging (EDIB), multilingualism and gender equity

DOAS is published as a document:

Consortium of the DIAMAS project. (2024). The Diamond OA Standard (DOAS)(1.2). Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.13820036>, and is operationalised as a self-assessment tool: <https://diamas.fecyt.es/> available to all Diamond OA publishers and service providers

This table provides an easy and quick insight into the structure of DOAS and helps you see what kind of information you need to provide and where you stand before taking the self-assessment.

There are two levels of compliance with DOAS: meeting the essential requirements (REQUIRED) and additional recommendations for further improvement (DESIRED).

Funding

01

Funding

Although Diamond OA is free to the author and reader, it has a cost. Quality criteria in this area are necessary to ensure that more equitable publishing can be financially sustained and developed in the short, medium and long term.

1.1. Diamond OA Model

Required

No paywalls. The publisher publishes its journals without charging fees to authors for publishing or to readers for reading.

Transparency on paywalls. The publisher provides explicit information on its website that no fees are charged to either authors to publish or readers to read, as well as if there are any other types of fees involved.

1.2. Sustainability

Required

Financial support. The publisher is directly or indirectly funded by public funds or other revenue streams to enable free access to the author and reader, ideally covering all costs.

Desired

Costs. Costs are identified year-on-year. Publishers are able to plan their annual costs and to balance them with expected incomes and in-kind contributions using a tracking system, such as a budget.

Sustainability plan. The publisher considers the medium-term economic viability of its Diamond OA model. It has a clear overview of available funding sources and other relevant external and internal (in-kind) resources, aligned with set expectations of future maintenance and developmental costs. In achieving its goals, a publisher preferably deploys collaborative strategies and uses common open infrastructures, to cut costs and raise efficiency.

Desired

Transparency on funding. An explicit statement about the publisher's funding streams is available on the publisher website. The in-kind and voluntary contributions are acknowledged.

➤ **Learn more:** [Sustainability resources](#)

1.3. Editorial Independence

Required

Editorial operations. Editorial operations related to content and peer review are independent and free from influence from the bodies that financially support the publisher or bodies that support individual publications of the publisher.

Desired

Revenue streams. The origin of the revenue streams is in line with the values, expectations, and traditions in the disciplines the publisher is serving. They do not have an impact on editorial independence. Any conflicts of interest between additional revenue streams (including commercial activity) and authors, reviewers, or editors are clearly indicated.

Legal Ownership, Mission and Governance

02

Legal Ownership, Mission and Governance

To uphold the quality of Diamond open access publishing, it is essential to establish transparent, robust, and community-oriented ownership structures, mission, and governance mechanisms. Maintaining scholarly ownership in the public domain, and encouraging scholarly community control, accessibility, accountability, and collaboration to be promoted, is key for the ethos of Diamond OA publishing.

➤ [Learn more: Ownership and governance](#)

2.1. Ownership

Required

Scholarly community. The publisher of the journal must be owned by a public or not-for-profit organisation (or parts thereof) whose mission includes performing or promoting research and scholarship.

Ownership statement. The publisher has a defined statement about the ownership of the individual journals it publishes. It includes the legal parameters governing the relationship between the publisher and its published journals, the determination of ownership for each title, and the explicit definition of the rights/duties afforded to editors within the publisher in a precise and unambiguous articulation. This also includes details about the discontinuation of the individual journal, and the transfer and preservation of its assets.

Changes in ownership. Changes in the ownership, relationships and rights/duties must be handled with care and transparently by publishers. A change in the service provider (for example, publishing infrastructure) can be achieved without changing the journal title, owner, or publisher.

Transparency in ownership. The publisher offers information about its ownership structure on its website.

2.2. Governance

Required

Mission. All journals published by the publisher ensure that their mission statement, aims, or scope are easily accessible on their website, with a clear structure and content.

Selection procedure. The publisher makes sure that all its journals have procedures for the selection of members of editorial bodies that should include details of their mandate's length, the regular renewal process, and clearly defined procedures for the dissolution of the board. This information is displayed on each journal's website.

Co-publishing. The publisher makes sure that relationships among co-publishers are defined by a formal agreement. It is also clearly indicated that the publication is a co-publication on the publisher website.

Roles and responsibilities. All journals of the publisher must have a clear definition of the roles and responsibilities of the publisher, editorial bodies, owners and publishers towards authors, reviewers, readers and the scholarly community, journal and platform owners, publisher, and the public. Roles and responsibilities related to the peer review process are described in detail on the publisher's website, and crucial aspects of the peer review process must not be left to publication technicians or AI.

Desired

Scholarly community driven. The publisher's governance has mechanisms to liaise with scholarly community stakeholders and to allow their input on its strategic direction and decision-making. This information is displayed on the publisher's website.

Transparency in editorial board selection. The publisher must offer information about the editorial board selection protocol on its website.

➤ Guidelines:

[Implementing community-led governance in publishing services](#)

2.3. Relations with Service Providers (SPs)

Desired

Agreement between publisher and service providers. Publishers might have commercial and non-commercial relationships with various SPs that are responsible for distinct technical and non-technical aspects of the workflow (e.g. ownership of infrastructure, copy-editing and typesetting services used, etc.). The publisher is clear about the workflow and the use of SPs and relationships with them. These might be different for each SP and for different journals.

Agreement between the publisher's journals and service providers. The publisher has transparent protocols guiding relationships with all SPs involved in the production of individual journals based on the legal agreements.

Open Science Practices

03

Open Science Practices

The growth of Diamond OA publishing is strongly linked to the development of Open Science (OS) practices. OS refers to practices and methods based on transparency, collaboration, and openness in scientific research. These practices make research more accessible, reproducible, and impactful by promoting the sharing of data, methods, and results.

➤ [Learn more: Open Science Practices](#)

3.1. Open Policies

Required

Open Access. The publisher publishes its journals in OA.

Facilitating compliance with OA mandates. The publisher enables compliance of their authors with the open access mandates of their funding agencies, as well as the institutional, and/or national OA policies regarding journal articles.

Underlying research data. Recognising the essential role of the availability of the article's underlying data in supporting conclusions and reproducibility, the publisher implements an output-level policy for this data in all its journals. This policy can be different for different journals. This information is displayed on the publisher/journal website.

Desired

Open Science policy. The publisher has an OS policy that shows it is aware of the value of the OS and understands what it entails.

Data policy content. The publisher's policy encourages the submission of underlying data for publications to be available to editors and reviewers during the manuscript review process. Additionally, it stipulates that this data will be accessible to all individuals by the time of publication in a FAIR manner through repositories, providing persistent identifiers (PIDs) and their connection from the publication to the data and from the data to the publication, and publicly available metadata. (DESIRED)

Desired

Research protocols and methods. The publisher has an output-level policy on research protocols and methods availability for all its journals. It encourages sharing them in public repositories, using PIDs for making the relevant connections. This is a good open science practice that allows others to replicate and build on published work. This information is displayed on the publisher's website.

Open research software. To facilitate reproducibility and FAIRification of research, the publisher encourages the use of free/open-source software. To this end, in all its journals, it defines a policy on the availability of research software and asks authors for a statement of availability.

Publication and sharing of negative scientific results. publishers acknowledge that the publication of negative or unexpected scientific results and data that do not confirm the initial hypotheses and experimental designs of the authors contribute to the advancement of science and scholarship.

➤ Guidelines:

[Research data sharing policy](#)

[Availability of research protocols, methods and software](#)

[Handling negative research results](#)

3.2. Authors' Rights, Intellectual Property Rights, and Licensing

Required

Rights retention policy. The publisher guarantees that authors retain sufficient rights for their works to enable them to be openly accessible and immediately reusable, in all its journals.

Open Licence. All contributions are published under an open licence (preferably CC-BY) to ensure further reuse without restrictions.

Transparency on rights retention publication policy. Publishing agreements or terms of use describe the content ownership and reuse rights. This information is publicly available on the publisher's website.

Desired

Third-party copyright. The publisher has a clear policy on reusing third-party materials in journal articles and how to deal with all the complexities that arise from combining elements with different usage rights.

User's rights. The publisher provides their users with complete and reliable information about the terms of use of all its journals content and services through its website. Users' rights, conditions of reuse, and redistribution of content and metadata are clearly described and labelled in human and computer-readable form, using standardised systems of open licences and rights statements.

➤ Guidelines:

[Copyright, authors' rights policy](#)

[Use of open licenses in open access publishing](#)

3.3. Repositories

Required

Deposits of published articles. The publisher allows dissemination of the article preprint version at any time, the Author Accepted Manuscript (AAM) version after acceptance, and/or the Version of Record (VoR) after publication in an Open Access repository of the authors' choice. The publisher may require authors to choose repositories that guarantee that the final version of the work is referenced.

Desired

Acceptance of preprints. The publisher accepts the submission of unreviewed and peer-reviewed preprints that are already available on preprint servers or in open repositories.

➤ **Guidelines:**
[Self-archiving policy](#)
[Preprints](#)

Editorial Management, Editorial Quality and Research Integrity

04

Editorial Management, Editorial Quality and Research Integrity

Editorial management, editorial quality, and research integrity are key pillars of all scholarly publishing models. These elements guarantee credibility and a high-quality, trustworthy scholarly communication system.

➤ Guidelines:

Basic editorial information that should be displayed

Diamond OA policies

4.1. Editorial Bodies

Required

Editorial independence. Editors-in-chief and/or Editorial Board have full responsibility over the entire editorial content of each journal published by the publisher.

Editorial bodies transparency. All journals of the publisher have a clearly defined and publicly displayed composition and constitution of its editorial bodies including: the names of the members of the editorial bodies and their affiliations; their editorial functions and roles; their PIDs and links to their institutional profiles to unambiguously specify the identity and affiliation of individual editorial bodies and board members.

Communication procedures between journals and the publisher. There are established procedures to facilitate communication between the editorial bodies of each individual journal and the publisher. These procedures aim to discuss political, commercial, or other incidents that might compromise the scientific credibility of the publication. They also facilitate the agreement on collaborative measures to ensure that such incidents do not influence the editor's decisions. Correspondence between referees, authors and publishers is subject to legal protection and kept confidential as needed.

Required

Skills/training. The publisher supports and/or provides continuous community-oriented training and education of journal editors and authors, which is essential in navigating the rapidly changing scholarly communication environment. The publisher promotes high-quality, inclusive, and impactful academic publishing practices by equipping stakeholders with the knowledge and skills necessary to adapt to technological, ethical, and policy changes and open science principles.

Desired

Engaging stakeholders. The publisher supports and encourages its stakeholders' engagement in initiatives, communities and associations promoting high-quality publishing practices and open science principles.

4.2. Peer Review

Required

Peer review. The publisher guarantees that all submitted manuscripts undergo a rigorous evaluation process before and/or after publication that is in line with accepted practices in the relevant discipline. This evaluation process can involve peer review, or another type of evaluation by more than one competent person who has no conflict of interest with the author(s).

Peer-review policy and procedures. The publisher guarantees that all its journals' websites publish a policy describing the evaluation or peer review process (both internal and external), indicating whether it is double-anonymous, single-anonymous, open peer review, etc., and specifying the tasks expected of reviewers. It will indicate whether reviews will be public or not (in which case, it will be specified whether they are transmitted to the author in full or edited). It also specifies the type of manuscript evaluation process. Evaluation can take place before or after publication, depending on the peer review model adopted: pre-publication peer review, post-publication peer review (Publish, Review, Curate – PRC – models), etc.

Required

Lack of endogeny. The publisher guarantees that manuscripts being reviewed by a closed circle of people who are well acquainted with each other or work in the same institution are minimised. The publisher is also proactively highlighting when an editorial board member publishes in their own journal and how they recused themselves from the usual editorial and peer review process, providing this information at the article level for relevant articles. A formal recusal process is also described in the editorial policy to help manage a potential Conflict of Interest of an editor or reviewer and avoid receiving preferential treatment.

Desired

Open peer review. The publisher provides reviewers of all its journals with the possibility of publishing and/or signing their reviews (either with their identity only visible to the editor, author, and the other reviewers, or with their identity visible to all readers), and/or the publisher makes reviews publicly available to a broader community.

Other contributors' copyright. The publisher guarantees that reviewers and other contributors hold the copyright of their reviews and contributions, and that editorial bodies and institutions retain ownership of all correspondence and mailing lists compiled on the online submission system put at their disposal by the publisher for all its journals.

Acknowledgement of reviewers. The publisher guarantees that all its journals publish the list of reviewers (with their consent) on a regular basis, at least every three years.

Incentives and rewards. The publisher has an incentives and rewards policy available to all its journals that guarantees reviewers get proper acknowledgement and reward editorial work as an academic activity by the institution employing the editor.

4.3. Editorial Quality

Required

Guidelines for author(s). The publisher guarantees that all its journals have clear guidelines for authors on its website. These guidelines must contain information on: how to submit manuscripts; formats of accepted files; supplementary materials and accepted data files; style guidelines and manuscript writing requirements for the correct preparation of titles, abstracts, keywords, professional affiliation, and bibliographic references; the editorial process followed by submissions: criteria for acceptance or editorial flow, review process, proofreading, estimated time between each part of the process, review protocols, and selection and publication criteria.

Guidelines for reviewers. The publisher provides reviewers with clear instructions and guidance (reviewing forms, free text options, and checklists) on the journal's aims and scope and what is expected of them in the review process.

Manual of style. The publisher guarantees that each of its journals apply a manual of style. It includes the appropriate use of symbols, units, nomenclature, statistics, standards, and similar items, specifying the citation style adopted.

Suitable layout. The publisher guarantees that each of its journals have a homogeneous layout.

Proofreading correction. The publisher ensures that standard copy-editing and proofreading procedures are applied in all journals.

Languages of submission. The publisher guarantees that all its journals clearly indicate on their website the languages in which manuscripts can be submitted.

Publishing timelines. The publisher ensures that all its journals have a regular schedule of publication, either issue by issue or via continuous publication. Continuous publication is recommended in the interest of Open Science. The date of submission, acceptance and publication is visible for each article.

➤ **Learn more:** [Editorial Quality](#)

4.4. Research Integrity

Required

Research and publication ethics. The publisher guarantees that all its journals adhere to international standards and codes of ethics or have their own publicly accessible code of ethics. This information is displayed on the publisher's website.

Conflict of interest. The publisher guarantees that all its journals have consistent workflows requiring authors, editors, and reviewers to disclose general and financial conflicts of interest or the absence thereof (i.e. in the Conflict-of-Interest statement). This information is displayed on the publisher's website.

Misconduct policy. The publisher guarantees that all its journals have a policy on how plagiarism, fabrication (making up data), falsification (manipulating materials, equipment, data, images or processes), complaints, appeals/allegations of research misconduct, and corrections, withdrawals and retractions are handled. This policy is displayed on the publisher's website.

Desired

Guidelines for authorship and/or contributorship. The publisher provides authorship and/or contributorship guidance, respecting the norms of relevant research disciplines. Contributions for deserving authorship include not only the writing but also the activities related to the conceptualisation and execution of the research, collection and production of the research data/materials, analysis and interpretation. Agreement on how these contributions will be acknowledged in the publication must be reached before submission of the manuscript, preferably early in the research process. The publisher supports good communication between all parties within the research to prevent or resolve possible disputes and authorship manipulation. The contribution of each researcher/collaborator should be published in the journal article.

Guidelines for Artificial Intelligence. The publisher has a guideline on generative AI tools, respecting changes of the research process in a technology-enhanced environment, and is informing and educating researchers/authors, reviewers and editors about responsible use of generative AI tools. This policy is displayed on the publisher's website.

➤ **Learn more:** [Research Integrity](#)

Technical Service Efficiency

05

Technical Service Efficiency

Ensuring the efficiency of technical services is crucial for sustaining the functionality of publication platforms and safeguarding the security of scientific outputs. This not only fosters collaboration and transparency but also guarantees the accessibility and long-term preservation of research results through interoperability and proper maintenance practices. These efforts collectively guarantee a resilient and sustainable ecosystem for Diamond open access scholarly publishing.

➤ **Learn more:**
[Software and Interoperability](#)

5.1. Publishing Infrastructure

Required

Use of platform. The publisher guarantees that a digital publishing platform supports online submission, editorial, and publishing workflows of all its journals.

Security. The publisher ensures that the infrastructure complies with the security standards established by law. When no standard exists in the region, the publisher will apply at least those measures necessary and sufficient to keep the system protected from malicious intrusions.

Basic functionalities. The publisher guarantees that all its publishing platforms have basic functionalities like assisting in the publishing workflow, being compliant with standards, allowing multilingual support, preferably including an accessible, responsive and usable interface, being interoperable or being able to support rich metadata.

Basic infrastructure management. The publisher guarantees that all its publishing platforms are well maintained, updated, regularly backed up and protected against security threats.

Long term preservation. The publisher has a publicly displayed archival and digital preservation policy which is consistently implemented. The published content is deposited in at least one digital preservation service.

Desired

Documentation. The publisher guarantees that all its journals are supplied with user instructions and documentation for editorial staff and end users and have a General Terms and Conditions for the use of the publishing infrastructure or platform. This information is displayed on their website.

Advanced functionalities. The publisher guarantees (where relevant) that all its publishing platforms offer advanced functionalities like post-publication evaluation and commenting, support for multimedia, and open peer review.

Advanced infrastructure management. The publisher guarantees that all its publishing platforms are maintained and developed following best practices and standards for IT service management to ensure improved efficiency, quality and consistency, risk reduction, and continuous improvement.

➤ **Guidelines: [Choosing a platform](#)**

5.2. Interoperability and Metadata

Required

Core metadata. The publisher guarantees that all its journals provide the following essential metadata on landing pages and via metadata exchange protocols, in human and machine-readable formats and under CC0 licence for each published item: title, full names and institutional affiliations – including country/region – of all author(s)/contributor(s), abstracts and keywords, funding information (as a minimum the name of the funder and the grant number/identifier), and information about the open access status, copyright holder and licensing.

Persistent identifiers. The publisher guarantees that all its journals provide a dedicated unique URL (landing page) and a persistent identifier for each published item. Standard numbers and other persistent identifiers for articles, contributors, as well as other relevant persistent identifiers, are also provided in human and machine-readable formats.

Registration of persistent identifiers. The publisher guarantees that the article identifiers are registered with registration agencies immediately at publication.

Required

Registration of persistent identifiers. The publisher guarantees that the article identifiers are registered with registration agencies immediately at publication.

Desired

Interoperability protocols. The publisher guarantees that all its publishing platforms support widely adopted metadata exchange protocols (OAI-PMH, API) and most usual metadata schemas. The publisher's platforms also support bulk export of metadata, and they indicate on their website which interoperability protocols are used and how to access them.

Complete metadata. Complete metadata, including bibliographic references, are immediately deposited in a registration agency in line with open metadata initiatives.

Text and data mining. The publisher guarantees that all its publishing platform supports automatic downloading, extraction and indexing of the full texts and the associated metadata with the aim of improving the visibility and usability of the published content.

Formats. The publisher guarantees that all its journals tag their full-text content in interoperable formats and provide access in multiple digital formats (e.g. PDF, HTML, XML, ePub, etc.), at least one of which is suitable for preservation.

Personal Data Protection. The publisher guarantees that all its journals comply with the General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR) as well as all relevant personal data regulations. This policy is displayed on the publisher's website.

➤ Learn more:

[Metadata](#)

[Preservation and content formats](#)

➤ Guidelines

[Metadata formats and export, identifiers, CRediT tags, bibliographic references, JATS XML or equivalent](#)

[GDPR and Personal data](#)

5.3. Collaboration

Desired

Open source. The publisher strives to ensure that the publishing infrastructure of all its journals is based on free and open-source software, with publicly available code. This facilitates interoperability, the sharing of expertise, and collaboration between publishers, while at the same time allowing them to retain know-how and technological autonomy to avoid vendor lock-in and adapt developments to their local needs.

Return to the community. The publisher participates in the development community by contributing bugs detected, translations into local languages, documentation, bug fixing or developments to promote collective growth.

Visibility, Communication, Marketing, and Impact

06

Visibility, Communication, Marketing, and Impact

Enhancing visibility, communication, marketing, and impact are essential imperatives for all scholarly communication to be effective. These practices enable scholars to amplify the reach and influence of their research.

➤ **Learn more:**

[Visibility, indexation, communication, marketing and impact](#)

6.1. Presence

Required

Visibility. The publisher makes sure that reasonable technical measures are taken towards improving the visibility of all its journals in search engines (general and academic), and aggregators.

Discoverability. The publisher works to increase the discoverability of its published content by registering its platform for harvesting by relevant discovery services and aggregator databases, and by submitting its journals to abstracting and indexing databases and citation indexes.

6.2. Collaboration

Desired

Communication channels. The publisher provides all its journals with unhindered and reliable channels for communication and dissemination of their content to academia and society at large. The use of social media and social networking, collaboration with the media and the use of traditional and modern dissemination methods, which help spread the content to a broader audience, are guided by the publishers' dissemination policies.

Desired

Community management. The community of users of the publisher's services is regularly informed of developments, policy changes, updates, new features, and functionalities, as well as about new publications. All the information provided by the publisher is accurate, reliable, regularly updated, and not misleading in any way.

Marketing. The publisher engages in appropriate and well-targeted promotional activities (including solicitation of manuscripts for their publications). It must support the promotion of all its journals' published content (e.g. by inviting post-publication reviews of outputs, inviting and moderating post-publication online comments, writing press releases, working with the media) in order to reach broader sectors of society.

Visual identity. The publisher provides a common visual identity for all its journals (e.g. by logos, corporate images, colours, etc.).

➤ Guidelines:

Marketing, communication and visibility

6.3. Analysis

Desired

Metrics. The publisher guarantees that all its journals offer comprehensive, accurate and reliable metric indicators detailing content usage, (e.g. article-level metrics: visits, views, downloads, citations), along with publication-level metrics, altmetric indicators, and geographical distribution of visitors.

Analytical tools. The publisher is clear on the analytical tools, algorithms, methodologies and/or external service providers that are employed for data generation and collection. This requirement is aligned with data protection regulation.

**Equity, Diversity,
Inclusion, and
Belonging (EDIB),
Gender, and
Multilingualism**

07

Equity, Diversity, Inclusion, and Belonging (EDIB), Gender, and Multilingualism

Publishers raise awareness among authors, members of editorial boards (and any supporting committees), peer reviewers, and journal staff on the diversity and pluralism of the stakeholders' linguistic, cultural, gender, academic, geographical, organisational, economic backgrounds, and accessibility.

➤ Learn more:

[Equity, Diversity, Inclusion and Belonging \(EDIB\)](#)

7.1. EDIB and Gender

Required

Equity in submissions and decisions. The publisher guarantees that all their journals accept submission of manuscripts within their thematic scope and language from all potential authors and that decision-making concerning content acceptance is without regard to authors' language, race, gender, age, sexual orientation, religious belief, ethnic origin, geographic location, or political philosophy.

Bias-free language. The publisher uses bias-free language related to age, disability, gender, racial and ethnic identity, sexual orientation, and socioeconomic status in all its communications and public information.

Research data sensitiveness. The publisher guarantees that all its journals require authors to inform whether the underlying research data of their publications are sensitive to age, disability status, sex, gender identity, racial and ethnic identity, sexual orientation, and /or socioeconomic status.

Desired

EDIB policy at the publisher level. The publisher has a policy that sets principles, commitments and actions for promoting EDIB in terms of linguistic, gender, cultural, academic, geographical, organisational, economic backgrounds and disabilities within its governing and management bodies, its editorial staff and boards, as well as reviewer pools and author's pool. It includes a Gender Equity Plan (GEP). This information is displayed on the publisher's website.

EDIB monitoring. The publisher monitors progress in its journals' EDIB policies and GEP. For that purpose, it collects and makes available data on gender balance, on country of origin, on organisational affiliation, and on the proportion of early career researchers (1-7 years from degree) among the members of the governing and management bodies, of the editorial staff and boards, of the reviewer pools and of the authors' pool. This is done without detracting from individuals' rights to not report some of this data if they don't wish to.

➤ **Learn more:** [Gender diversity](#)

➤ **Guidelines:** [Gender diversity](#)

7.2. Accessibility

Required

Accessible website. The publisher guarantees that its websites and those of the journals are accessible under the terms of applicable international, national or local laws and policies.

Desired

Monitoring. The publisher collects and makes available data on the amount of feedback received relating to shortcomings in all their journals' accessibility standards, as well as a record of improvements to the standards.

➤ **Guidelines:** [Accessible/inclusive website, content and metadata](#)

7.3. Multilingualism

Required

Full text. The publisher's journals can publish full texts in more than one language, either bilingual, simultaneously as separate documents in the same journal, or sequentially in other journals.

Website and content. The publisher recommends that all its journals' websites offer multilingual content. The information given on the site must be the same in all languages.

Desired

Abstracts. The publisher guarantees that all its journals facilitate that abstracts are published in at least two languages, where relevant.

Plain language summary. The publisher guarantees that all its journals provide a plain language summary alongside the traditional scientific abstract.

Translation. The publisher guarantees that all its journals provide support for human translation and language-check services to authors.

Language technologies. The publisher encourages all its journals to integrate a computer assisted translation (CAT) tool/solution on the website if tools that can provide sufficiently good translations are available and encourages journals to provide machine-translation friendly abstracts. Automatic machine translations will not be used for publishing manuscripts in language(s) other than the original without the supervision of translators and/or experts.

Metadata translation. The publisher recommends that all its journals offer metadata in English if the language of the text is not English.

➤ **Learn more:** [Multilingualism](#)

➤ **Guidelines:** [Multilingualism](#)

Partners

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DIAMAS

Developing Institutional Open Access
Publishing Models to Advance
Scholarly Communication

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